

Speculation of Spin Entropy for an Sz Eigenstate

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In (1), a formula for spin entropy is derived, but it seems this result predicts zero entropy for an Sz eigenstate described by the wavefunction $\exp(im\phi)$, where $m = -s$ to s in steps of 1 and s is the spin. We speculate that $\exp(im\phi)$ represents a uniform distribution of ϕ for an angle range of 0 to $2\pi/m$. This corresponds to a probability of $m/2\pi$ and an entropy of $-\ln(m/2\pi)$ using Shannon's entropy and integrating over $d\phi$. We speculate that there should be an intrinsic entropy for $\exp(im\phi)$. We have suggested, however, in (2) that entropy is linked to measurement and that as a result, one presents an entropy related to the measurement or interaction scheme which does not include all of the entropy present. For example, if an electron has E_n energy levels, linked to wavefunctions, $W_n(x)$, and it interacts with photons (jumping or dropping levels), then one does not consider the entropy of $W_n(x)$ itself (i.e. $-\int dx W_n(x)W_n^*(x) \ln(W_n(x)W_n^*(x))$) because one wishes to have a measure of the occupation of energy levels, not uncertainty within a level. Nevertheless, physically there seems to be entropy in any given state $W_n(x)$. This seems to be the same situation with $\exp(im\phi)$ and formula given in (1) for entropy.

Entropy Relative to the Measurement or Interaction

In (2), we suggested that one may write entropies linked to a measurement constraint. For example, for a free particle, $\exp(ip \cdot r)$, we argued that there existed an entropy of $-\ln(p/\hbar)$ along the p direction. This is linked to an impulse hit measurement in which the target is perpendicular to the direction of p . If one considers a target perpendicular to the x -axis, the only p_x is relative and the corresponding wavefunction is $\exp(ip_x x)$ with an associated entropy $-\ln(p_x/\hbar)$. In other words, this entropy does not describe the full entropy of the system, but is only relevant to the type of interaction present, i.e. a collision with a target perpendicular to the x -axis.

We argue that this is not the only case in which entropy is linked to the measurement or interaction situation. We consider an electron with energy levels E_n and wavefunctions, $W_n(x)$. In principle, one might suggest a spatial Shannon's entropy:

$$S_{\text{spatial}} = \int dx W^*W \ln(W^*W) \quad ((1))$$

A similar expression may be written for S_{momentum} using $a(p)$ with $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We have suggested before writing $S_{\text{spatial}} + S_{\text{momentum}}$.

If, however, one has an interaction involving excited states emitting photons and lower states absorbing them, then this interaction is associated with uncertainties in occupations of E_n levels. If one assumes that the profile of W_n does not affect the probability to absorb or emit a photon, then one is really considering an energy distribution problem with any absorption or emission having the same probability. In such a case, one uses Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics with E_n values to calculate the entropy and ignores ((1)). It is not that ((1)) does not describe

uncertainty, but it seems that it has nothing to do with the interactions present. It does not influence them one way or another. We suggest that another case is the spin entropy presented in (1).

Spin Entropy of (1)

In (1), an equation for spin entropy is presented as follows:

$$S = - \sum_{m=-s}^s |a(s,m)|^2 \ln\{ |a(s,m)|^2 \} - \int |b(\phi)|^2 \ln\{ |b(\phi)|^2 \} d\phi \quad ((2))$$

Here $b(\phi) = \sum_{m=-s}^s a(s,m) W(s,m)$ where $W(s,m) = \exp(i(s+m)\phi)$ for z in the northern part of a sphere and $\exp(i(-s+m)\phi)$ for z in the southern.

$a(s,m)$ is defined using an eigenstate of SS and Sz , i.e.

$$|state s\rangle = \sum_{m=-s}^s a(s,m) |s,m\rangle \quad \text{where } |s,m\rangle \text{ is an eigenstate of } SS, \text{ and } Sz$$

In other words, in all cases, one has sums of m , the z projection of spin. This suggests measurements or interactions related to changing the m projection. As a result, this entropy is associated with such a measurement or set of interactions.

We note that if one simply has $|s,m\rangle$, then $a(s,m)=1$ and $b(\phi) = \exp(i(s+m)\phi)$ for the northern part of the sphere and $b(\phi) = \exp(i(-s+m)\phi)$ for the southern.

Using these expressions, one finds that S given in ((2)) is 0 for $|s,m\rangle$. In other words, one does not have any interaction changing m and so there is no entropy or uncertainty with respect to m for a given s .

We suggest, however, that even for a fixed m , one has $\exp(i m \phi)$ and that this suggests uncertainty in ϕ . If one uses the northern part of the sphere, then $\exp(i (s+m) \phi)$ is the full expression. If one considers a fixed s in the northern part of the sphere and is interested in different m values there, then it seems that there is a entropy associated with a uniform probability distribution in ϕ ranging from $\phi=0$ to $\phi = 2\pi / m$. For example, for spin $1/2$, the range would be $\phi=0$ to 4π .

This would then lead to an intrinsic Shannon's entropy for $|s,m\rangle$ with s fixed of:

$$- \ln (m/(2\pi)) \quad ((3))$$

This intrinsic entropy is not included in ((2)), the result from (1), and we assume that this means that interactions which change the m projection (along z) are not influenced by the entropy ((3)). It does seem that just as in the case of $\exp(ip_x)$ or $W_n(x)$, an intrinsic entropy exists.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (2) we suggested that entropy is a measure of uncertainty linked to the measurement or interactions which occur. It does not describe all uncertainty in a system. In particular, we consider a formula for spin entropy given in (1) which gives 0 entropy for an eigenstate of S_S and S_z . This suggests that the interaction in question is one which changes m , i.e. projections along the z axis. The wavefunction in ϕ , $\exp(i m \phi)$ for a fixed s in the top part of a sphere, however, suggests uncertainty in ϕ . We suggest that even though this not included in ((2)), one may consider a uniform probability density for $\phi=0$ to $2\pi/m$ and suggest an intrinsic entropy of $-\ln(m/2\pi)$.

References

1. Geger, D. and Kedem, Z. Spin Entropy (2022) Entropy 2022, 24(9), 1292; <https://doi.org/10.3390/e24091292>
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